
Research

A Study on The Cross Cultural Adaptability of International Students in China

Mohammadi Hafizullah^{1*}, Hou Tao¹, Liu Rong¹

¹College Foreign Language Taiyuan University of Technology

Abstract: In recent years, with the improvement of China's comprehensive national strength and the promotion of the "the Belt and Road" initiative, the number of overseas students in China has been increasing. The cultural differences between different countries and regions lead to cultural conflicts for international students who come to China. This article analyzes the cultural adaptation barriers faced by international students from Chinese Universities in China in terms of communication, academic performance, thinking concepts, and social culture in a cross-cultural context, and proposes countermeasures from three levels: government, school, and individual. It emphasizes the importance of strengthening the international dissemination of Chinese Universities culture, establishing a reasonable education management system for international students, external support, and the knowledge reserves of international students themselves. Through joint efforts from multiple aspects, international students in China can quickly become familiar with, accept, and internalize Chinese culture, enhance their cultural identity, and achieve cross-cultural adaptation.

Keywords: China; Cultural adaptation; International students; Obstacles; Countermeasure

*Corresponding Author

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Introduction

As regional economic integration are gradually being implemented, China's international influence has significantly grown, leading to a continuous rise in the number of international students studying in China. Scholars have shown significant interest in the issues surrounding cross-cultural adaptation and the factors that influence the cross-cultural adaptation of international students in China. Cross-cultural adaptation refers to the process in which two groups, consisting of individuals with distinct cultural backgrounds, modify and conform to the original cultural framework during prolonged and continuous interaction. Nevertheless, scholars have divergent opinions regarding the categorization of cross-cultural adaptation. Ward categorizes cross-cultural adaptation into two distinct types: socio-cultural adaptation and psychological adaptation. Chen categorized the sociocultural adjustment of international students into seven distinct dimensions: adaptation to daily life, adaptation to social norms, adaptation to communication, adaptation to social support systems, adaptation to service modes, adaptation to the social environment, and adaptation to local customs and habits. Zhu incorporated academic adaptation, which encompasses both social-cultural adaptation and psychological adaptation. Wang categorized the process of social cultural

adaptation among international students in China into three dimensions: language, life, and culture. Additionally, he examined the four dimensions of psychological adaptation to study this cross-cultural adaptation. Psychological adaptation and social-cultural adaptation are two fundamental dimensions. The research on the factors that influence cross-cultural adaptation primarily focuses on analyzing macro and micro factors, also known as external and internal factors. Ward initially categorized the factors that affect cross-cultural adaptation into two levels: individual and social. Subsequently, through extensive research, he further classified these factors into specific cultural factors and general cultural factors. Researchers have categorized cross-cultural adaptation factors into internal and external factors. External factors encompass various elements such as life events, passage of time, social assistance, cultural disparity, discrimination, and bias. On the other hand, internal factors consist of cognitive assessment, individual disposition, knowledge, and abilities. The growing population of international students and their increasing demands for high-quality education have progressively enhanced the capacity of petroleum universities in China to educate foreign students, thereby presenting greater challenges to these institutions. The objective of this study is to investigate the factors that influence the cross-cultural adaptability of international students and offer recommendations to enhance their cross-cultural adaptability in China.

2. The current development status

In recent years, the scale of international students from Chinese Universities has been continuously expanding, and the service management system for studying abroad in China has gradually improved. Based on the "National Compilation of Chinese Universities Statistics", an objective analysis was conducted on the basic situation of international students from higher Chinese medicine universities nationwide. It was found that the education of international students from Chinese medicine universities in China presents the following characteristics:

Since the first batch of foreign students were admitted to Beijing University of Chinese Universities in 1957, the scale of international students in Chinese colleges has continued to expand. According to the latest data from the "National Compilation of Chinese Universities Statistics", the number of international students studying in higher education institutions of Chinese Universities in China has increased from 5631 in 2011 to 7439 in 2021, with an overall upward trend. Among them, undergraduate students are the main body. In 2021, there were 5674 undergraduate students studying abroad, accounting for approximately 76% of the total number.

2.1 Uneven distribution of student sources among international students studying in China

Due to the particularity of the discipline, there are more international students from Asian countries, and they are showing a growth trend. The number of people increased from 4861 in 2011 to 5847 in 2021. From different regions, the distribution of international students is very wide, with the highest proportion coming from Asia, reaching 81% in 2021; Next are international students from Europe and America, accounting for 11%; International students from Africa and Oceania account for 7% and 1% respectively. Although Chinese Universities education for studying abroad in Europe, America, and Oceania is gradually developing, the growth rate is relatively slow. In contrast, the number of students from African countries has increased significantly, reaching 502 in 2021, which is about five times the number in 2011 [5].

2.2 The educational levels of international students studying in China are diverse

In 2011, there were 5109 Chinese colleges and universities studying abroad in China, including 4024 undergraduate students, accounting for approximately 78.8%, 707 master's students, accounting for approximately 13.8%, 367 doctoral students, accounting for approximately 7.2%, and 11 vocational students, accounting for approximately 0.22%; 522 nonacademic students. In 2021, there were 7200 Chinese colleges and universities studying abroad in China, including 5674 undergraduate students, accounting for approximately 78.8%, 866 master's students, accounting for approximately 12%, 606 doctoral students, accounting for approximately 8.42%, and 54 vocational students, accounting for approximately 0.75%; 239 nonacademic students. In order to optimize the educational structure of international students and increase efforts to cultivate research talents in Chinese Universities for international students studying in China,

the number of master's level international students admitted by Chinese Universities colleges and universities increased in 2020, and the number of students enrolled also increased accordingly. From the above data, the educational levels of international students from Chinese colleges and universities in China are diverse and the structure is continuously optimized. Among the educated students, undergraduate students are the main group, and the number of master's and doctoral students has significantly increased, while the number of vocational students has also increased. This is not only related to the development of China's politics, economy, and other aspects, but also benefits from the strong implementation of the "going global" strategy of Chinese Universities and the internationalization of higher education in Chinese Universities.

In addition, there are still significant areas for improvement in the international education of Chinese Universities in China, including weak allocation of teaching resources, shortcomings in teaching teams, and the need to improve the quality of training. There is still room for improvement in service management systems and the integration of Chinese and foreign students.

3. The main cultural adaptation barriers

Cultural adaptation was first proposed in 1936, referring to all phenomena in which one or both cultural patterns of different cultural groups change during continuous cultural contact. With the deepening of academic research, its concept has differentiated into two levels: group and individual. The research object of this article is the group of international students from Chinese Universities universities studying in China, which is a group level study that focuses on the changes in the process of this group's exposure to new cultures [6].

3.1 Communication adaptation

International students face communication barriers during their study and life in China. International students studying in China must first pass the language proficiency test. Although international students studying in China have passed the HSK Level 4 exam, due to the complexity of Chinese language, it requires a long period of learning and practice to master and apply it proficiently. Therefore, the majority of international students have only a basic level of Chinese proficiency and face certain difficulties in expression and communication in their daily learning and life.

In addition to language adaptation difficulties, non-verbal communication barriers are also important issues faced by international students studying in China. International students who are unable to communicate with others through language may choose to use nonverbal means of communication, such as facial expressions, gestures, and body language. However, due to cultural differences between countries and regions, the understanding of body language may not be the same in different regions. Therefore, during communication, both parties may also be unable to correctly perceive the information and meaning conveyed by the other party.

3.2 Academic adaptation

Communication barriers have further caused academic adaptation difficulties for international students studying in China. In recent years, with the implementation of the "going global" strategy of Chinese Universities, its popularity in the international community has gradually increased, attracting more and more international students to study Chinese medicine related majors in China. However, Chinese Universities colleges often use Chinese language teaching for international students, and most international students are not yet proficient in Chinese, making it difficult to fully understand the professional terminology and theoretical system of Chinese Universities. International students studying Chinese Universities in China often face difficulties in learning and heavy academic tasks.

In addition, different educational models can also affect the academic adaptation of international students studying in China. There is a certain degree of heterogeneity in the education models of different countries. The Chinese teaching model focuses mainly on teacher instruction, with a greater emphasis on the learning of theoretical knowledge. After entering Chinese Universities colleges and universities, international students in China may have some discomfort with the teaching methods and content of the teachers. In addition, they may not communicate with their classmates and

teachers in a timely manner, which will to some extent increase their psychological pressure and affect their academic performance.

3.3 Adaptation of thinking concepts

The concept of thinking is also an aspect that Chinese medicine colleges and universities need to adapt to for international students studying in China. The origin, evolution, and inheritance of Chinese and Western civilizations have their own unique historical backgrounds and processes. Undergraduate students are the main group of international students from Chinese Universities colleges and universities in China. At this age, students have relatively fixed thinking concepts and face significant obstacles in accepting foreign ideas. As an excellent traditional Chinese culture, Chinese Universities culture has original characteristics. The Chinese Universities thinking methods such as Yin Yang, Five Elements, and Qi have also undergone evolution from philosophical categories to concepts, and have unique advantages. Although international students studying in Chinese Universities (TCM) colleges and universities may enter related majors, they lack understanding of TCM culture to a certain extent due to their own thinking concepts, making it difficult to deeply understand its true connotation and essence, and cannot quickly accept and form TCM thinking. Therefore, international students studying in China inevitably face obstacles in their thinking and concepts when adapting to Chinese culture.

3.4 Sociocultural adaptation

When international students move from their inherent cultural environment to a new cultural environment, they may experience cultural discomfort, namely facing cultural shock. When the new social culture is similar to the original culture, international students are more likely to accept and integrate into the new society; On the contrary, international students will develop a mentality of rejection and separation. China has a civilization history of five thousand years, and Confucian culture has always been the mainstream culture among them. Under the influence of Confucianism, China has gradually formed a social and cultural system with Chinese characteristics. The doctrine of the mean, the idea of unity, and the idea of benevolence in Confucianism have also had a profound impact on the diagnosis and treatment of Chinese Universities, models, and ethics, and have distinct characteristics of Chinese traditional culture. When international students from Chinese Universities universities come to China and meet Chinese social and cultural differences that differ greatly from their original culture, they have to adapt to a larger difficulty and span. This social and cultural difference leads to difficulties in cultural adaptation for international students studying in China.

4. Strategies for the Cultural Adaptation Dilemma

International students need to adapt to a new cultural environment in the early stages of studying abroad, which may lead to feelings of loneliness, anxiety, loss, and even affect their learning and life. The cultural adaptation barriers faced by international students studying in China should receive attention from all levels of society. To alleviate the pressure on international students studying in China, the government, schools, and individuals need to find timely response strategies to ensure the quality of learning and physical and mental health of international students, and promote cross-cultural exchange.

4.1 At the government level

4.1.1 Strengthen the international dissemination of Chinese Universities culture

Before studying Chinese Universities systematically in China, most international students receive modern education and have little understanding of Chinese Universities concepts such as yin and yang, five elements, and the unity of heaven and man. This directly limits the formation of their Chinese Universities thinking and their understanding of Chinese Universities culture. To enhance the international dissemination of Chinese Universities culture, it is necessary to broaden the channels of dissemination. With the help of the Internet and new media, scientific, rigorous and interesting content is selected to integrate Chinese medicine culture into the lives of international people, improve their interest, and enhance their acceptance of Chinese medicine concepts and thinking. At the same time, the government also needs to further enrich the forms and carriers of international dissemination of Chinese Universities culture, and

improve the effectiveness of international dissemination. For example, by releasing high-quality documentaries on Chinese Universities overseas, publishing comics and other works with the theme of Chinese Universities culture, explaining Chinese Universities theory and culture in popular language and acceptable ways, enhancing international public awareness of Chinese Universities culture, and achieving true international dissemination of Chinese Universities culture.

4.1.2 Establish a scholarship and funding system

At present, China has established three different types of scholarships for international students studying in China: Chinese government scholarships, local government scholarships, and university scholarships. Scholarships have played a good role in expanding the scale of international students and optimizing the structure. The higher the expectations of students for obtaining scholarships, the greater the value of scholarships, and the more motivated they are to strive for them, thus enabling them to exert the motivating effect of scholarships [12] For international students in difficult economic situations, the government should actively formulate temporary assistance and assistance policies, collaborate with local communities and universities to implement the policies, and reduce the economic pressure on international students. In addition, a government led scholarship funding system should be established with the participation of enterprises, industry organizations, and schools. The scope of scholarship funding should be expanded, and scholarships should be established and distributed based on the comprehensive abilities, academic performance, and poverty level of international students. This will enhance the ability of students studying in China to cope with risks and enhance their ability to learn and spread Chinese Universities culture.

4.2 At the school level

4.2.1 Enriching Campus Academic Activities of Chinese Universities Culture

International students studying in China have shown a strong interest in academic activities related to Chinese Universities and a strong willingness to participate in high-level seminars, academic forums, and other activities organized by the school. Therefore, universities should actively carry out large-scale cutting-edge academic activities on Chinese Universities and encourage international students to actively participate. This not only promotes the formation of a research environment to a certain extent, but also enhances the acceptance of Chinese Universities culture among international students. At the same time, schools should hold more lectures on Chinese Universities, set up exchange centers for international students, and encourage clubs and students to hold targeted cultural exchange activities. Through these activities, we aim to cultivate and strengthen the interest of international students in Chinese Universities, enhance cross-cultural interaction, enhance their identification with Chinese Universities culture, encourage them to actively establish friendly relationships with Chinese students, and enhance their adaptability and sense of belonging to the school.

4.2.2 Building a professional team of teaching staff for Chinese medicine international students

High quality education is an important guarantee for promoting students to study abroad in China, and also one of the important factors in attracting overseas students. In recent years, China has successively introduced policies to strengthen the overall strength and international competitiveness of its higher education, and achieve the transformation from a higher education powerhouse to a higher education powerhouse. Therefore, cultivating a professional team of international student teachers is crucial for improving the learning ability and educational quality of international students. Teachers of international students in Chinese Universities colleges and universities not only need to master the basic knowledge of Chinese Universities and understand the cultural background of Chinese Universities, but also need to have a broad international perspective, rich clinical practice experience, and strong teaching skills, familiar with the needs and learning habits of international students. At the same time, universities should also attach importance to providing cross-cultural, language, emergency measures, information technology and other training for teachers, and build a high-level and composite team of teaching staff for Chinese medicine international students.

4.2.3 Establish a reasonable and scientific management system for international students

On the basis of building a professional team of teaching staff for Chinese medicine international students, Chinese medicine colleges should also establish a reasonable and scientific management system for international students based on actual situations and strictly implement it, including student enrollment, student visas, daily management, student welfare and rights protection, etc. Chinese Universities colleges should also establish specialized institutions for managing international students, responsible for formulating, implementing, supervising, and evaluating policies for managing international students. In addition, it is necessary to designate relevant personnel to ensure the normal operation of the management organization. In terms of recruiting international students, there should be clear standards and procedures, and the application materials and qualifications of students should be reviewed through a unified entrance and standardized exams. The admitted international students should meet the requirements, have the ability to complete the study abroad plan, and have the ability to ensure safety.

4.3 On a personal level

Solving the cultural adaptation issues of international students in China not only requires the efforts of the government and schools, but also requires the students themselves and teachers to find solutions at the individual level. Meanwhile, family support is an indispensable aspect in ensuring the normal learning and life of international students.

4.3.1 Teacher: Innovative teaching methods

Chinese Universities culture has a long history and profound heritage, and its way of thinking and values are the most core part of learning related to Chinese Universities. When teaching Chinese Universities knowledge to international students, teachers should not only pay attention to the explanation of Chinese Universities theory, but also focus on cultivating students' Chinese Universities thinking concepts. For international students from different cultural backgrounds, teachers can adopt diverse teaching methods, such as telling stories about the ethics and style of famous doctors, screening documentaries on Chinese Universities, and using easy to understand language to interpret Chinese Universities classics. At the same time, teachers can innovate teaching methods by incorporating discussions, group learning, and other activities in the classroom, promoting international students to form their own thinking and understanding of Chinese Universities thinking and theory. Immersive teaching experience can enable international students to have a deeper understanding of Chinese Universities thinking concepts, improve their cognitive level of Chinese Universities culture, stimulate learning interest and enthusiasm, and lay a good foundation for forming Chinese Universities thinking. Chinese Universities, as a highly practical profession, teachers not only need to innovate theoretical teaching methods, but also expand practical aspects to enrich the clinical experience of international students. They can regularly organize hospital internships, conduct case studies, participate in community free clinics, and carry out clinical internships and other practical activities. Based on the actual situation of international students, carefully formulate corresponding teaching plans, continuously improve the teaching quality of practical courses, and enhance their professional skills in Chinese Universities. At the same time, teachers should also pay attention to the personal differences of international students and carry out personalized teaching to promote their mastery of Chinese Universities knowledge and skills.

4.3.2 International students: Prepare knowledge reserves before studying abroad

Knowledge reserve refers to the knowledge that international students need to master in the target country's language, local customs and habits, environment, especially the relevant situations and social culture that are different from those in China before heading to their destination. In order to quickly adapt to the Chinese environment, international students can learn about China's history, customs, and social systems in advance by reading relevant books or materials, which can help them adapt to the environment faster and better. At the same time, international students can learn about the cultural characteristics, teaching management, academic requirements, and other aspects of the target Chinese medicine university by consulting its official website or communicating with full-time personnel, in order to quickly integrate into the learning and living environment of the university and successfully complete their studies. Therefore,

international students studying in China should prepare their knowledge in advance, which can not only reduce the sense of unfamiliarity caused by the foreign environment and the impact of cultural shock, but also provide a better learning and living experience.

4.3.3 Family: Provide spiritual and material support to international students studying in China

Family is the main way for international students to receive emotional support in China. After arriving in China, some international students experience varying degrees of academic and psychological problems due to differences between the original culture and the new culture. Before international students go abroad, parents must establish a good family relationship with their children and help them establish a sense of security. After studying abroad, parents should provide their children with more emotional support and strengthen communication and interaction with them. Especially when they feel uncomfortable in China, parents should patiently listen to their stories, analyze problems with them, provide opinions and suggestions, and provide spiritual and material support. At the same time, international students should actively establish positive communication with their families and actively enhance their connections with them.

5. Conclusion

At present, studying abroad education has become one of the important factors in evaluating a country's soft power and international influence. The issue of learning and life adaptation for international students in China cannot be ignored. Cultural adaptation is a problem that international students must face and solve in the process of living and learning in a foreign country. Only by achieving cultural adaptation can international students better integrate into Chinese society, learn and master Chinese Universities knowledge, and also promote the exchange and integration of Chinese and Western cultures. Chinese Universities colleges and universities should strive to eliminate cultural barriers for international students, enhance their adaptability in cross-cultural environments, and continuously promote mutual respect, understanding, and identification between different cultures through active foreign exchange activities, gradually improving China's international education level and enhancing China's international influence.

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